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Nigeria Energy Transition Plan: Pathways for Renewable Energy Sources Expansion

Prepared and Presented by;

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Country Flag

1. Context

Nigeria's current population is 223.8 Million (UNFPA, 2023)
 Population rate is higher than electrification rate; Ratio 2.5 to 1.1
 Nigeria's electricity access rate is about 52%(According to UN Tracking SDG Goal 7 report for 2022)
 The identified hydroelectricity sites have an estimated capacity of about 14,250 MW
 Average electricity supply from the grid to household per day is 8-10hours
 86% of rural households in Nigeria depend on fuel wood as their source of energy
 In 2019 Nigeria had 22 million petrol generators (Dalberg, 2019)
 Nigerians spend \$12 billion each year on buying and operating small gasoline generators (Dalberg, 2019)

2. Aim

to investigate possible energy transition pathways that will provide valuable insights for strategic clean energy policies that both meet Nigeria's energy demand and cut emissions in the power sector.

Figure #. Caption.

3. Methods & Scenarios

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
BAU	No new investments in renewable power generation, electric stoves and heating, electric transport or energy efficiency are permitted.	Significant investment in renewable energy expansion will not happen without policy interventions and an evaluating tool/model.
LC	Implementation of energy efficiency measures across all sectors to reduce the use of fossil fuel consumption and associated emissions.	Significant deployment of renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, and hydropower, to replace fossil fuel-based power generation
Expansion Future	Promoting and establishing clear and consistent policy frameworks that incentivize low-carbon investments and technologies to achieve net-zero in year 2060.	Significant robust policies and regulatory frameworks that promote renewable energy development would attract private sector investments, and create a favorable business environment.

4. Results

5. Policy insights, conclusions and future work

In conclusion, expanding renewable energy is not only an imperative but a tremendous opportunity for improving access rates and transforming our energy landscape. By prioritizing renewable energy expansion, we can achieve multiple benefits simultaneously. We can reduce our reliance on fossil fuels, increase access to electricity, and foster a more sustainable and resilient energy system..

Future Work

- We employ the government and International Institutions to invest in RE pilot projects which would encourage private investors to invest in RE.
- The Nigeria Sustainable Energy for All platform should be regularly updated to monitor and track progress.
- The model is a work in progress and we believe that in future work we would take into account all parameters that may not enable the net-zero target.

6. References

- [1] Nigeria Renewable Energy Action Plan
- [2] Nigeria National Sustainable Energy for All Action Agenda
- [3] <http://www.nigerianmuse.com/20100221082947zg/nigeria-watch/historical-compedium-of-rulers-of-states-in-nigeria>

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